

Mission-Oriented Synodal Church

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Abstract

Every individual is on a mission, entrusted to him/her by Christ. But he/she is part of a larger community with a mission of Christ. The universal nature of the Church makes it a large community with one purpose to be another Christ to the neighbour. The Gospels show us how Christ himself was universal in his approach. He was a man of community and the community that he formed was a community on the move, a dynamic community. The desire of individuals is to be like Christ thus maintaining their individualness and proclaiming him to the world. I am the mission to the other as well as to myself. I am a part of the community, and hence the community is the mission; Moreover, the community is part of Christ, and hence Christ is the mission. Thus, the mission of the synodal Church today is to be a community knit together with a mission of being Christ-like to others.

Introduction

The Church provides to its faithful the real presence of Christ as it continues the work of Christ in the world in a tangible manner. The work of the Church is seen as a continuation of the work of Christ. Though the Church is the Mystical Body of Christ led by Jesus and sustained by the Spirit, the Church is also very human. It has members who belong to his family through the sacrament of baptism. Hence, it is prerogative to understand the role of an individual within the Church in the context of the mission of the whole Church. Thus, the mission of the Church has an individual as well as a communitarian dimension.

With Pope Francis' call to Synodality, the Church is asserting this mission towards one another and towards a larger society, irrespective of their belief system. The three-pronged approach of the Synod that calls for

communion, participation, and mission is well focused on the key characteristics of the Church. Vatican II, defined as the Council ‘of the Church,’ ‘of Christ,’ ‘of man,’ provided a pathway in understanding the mission of every individual belonging to the larger community, the family of Christ. *Lumen Gentium* 9 stated that the Church as the people of God is “established by Christ as a communion of life, charity and truth, it is also used by Him as an instrument for the redemption of all, and is sent forth into the whole world as the light of the world and the salt of the earth.” It emphasized all the three aspects of communion, participation and mission. The Church which is a community needs to participate in the mission of Christ. It’s primary purpose of existence is to carry forward the work of Christ in a manner which Christ himself suggests through the Gospels. The Church is a community of faithful disciples with a communitarian responsibility to promote Christ who himself is the mission.

Universal Nature of Church’s Mission

The Church’s mission, as we know, is universal in nature. Her mission is not limited to any singular culture or political or economic or social system. The Church enters into communion with all cultures and moreover places on its members a responsibility to move into participatory dialogue with others so as to make Christ’s mission their own. Jesus in meeting the Samaritan woman (Jn 4:5-42), the Syro-Phoenician woman (Mk 7:24-31), the Centurion (Lk 7:1-10), the demoniac of Gadarenes (Mk 5:1-20), the Canaanite woman with a troubled daughter (Mt 15:21-28) and many such so-called gentiles of his time, displays that his mission was universal. In its approach towards humanity, the Church also follows Christ in its attitude of being universal in nature. Therefore, the Synodic nature of the Church is intrinsic to itself. It cannot but reach out to others irrespective of their beliefs. Its primary focus is to be and remain synodal in its approach towards all. Hence it is a universal community to which it reaches out since its very nature is universal and its approach inclusive.

Mission – You and Me

On the 92nd World Mission Day, Pope Francis emphatically stated that ‘Every man and woman is a mission.’ This statement is loaded with meaning. It can be understood in two ways. Mission is something that is external to us, namely the other, but it can also mean that I am the mission. If every man and woman is a mission I fall into that category wherein for the other I am the mission and for me the other is the mission, moreover I am a mission to myself. This circular pattern of understanding mission leads to the fact that every Christian bears a responsibility towards oneself and the others as a baptized person. Christ’s

incarnation makes him one with us as a human, and hence He, in the other, becomes our mission and he within us through his Eucharistic presence makes us a mission to the other. The correct understanding of our mission is provided to us in and through the incarnation of Christ wherein the whole of humanity is called to be another Christ. As disciples of Jesus being distinct from him, we are to carry forward his work under his banner. The mission is to be Christ to others. Jesus states, 'you shall be my witnesses' (Acts 1:8) thus emphasizing upon the fact that the 'you' can be anyone who believes in him and the 'witnesses' are the ones who recognize him in the neighbour.

Community in Mission

There are many references in the Bible to the communitarian aspect of Jesus' ministry. He called twelve apostles (Mk 3:13-19), sent them two by two (Mk 6:7, Lk 10:1), he sent them to towns (Lk 10:10), told them to stay with families (Lk 10:7), and moreover, their mission was to one and all. The term mission has its root in the Hebrew term 'שלח' (shalách), meaning to send, stretch out, extend, send away, set free. The sending is with an imperative force of going on behalf of someone or rather following the order of another. Thus a missionary is not doing his will but rather the will of the one who sent him/her. It is Christ who sends us on a mission. It is his mission and we are merely following orders. Does this mean that our participation has no value or that the missionary has no say in the matter? It is not so since the one sent has complete control over himself and surrenders his/her will to the sender. Understanding the sender's mind means that the one who is sent understands oneself. That's what is to be understood when St. Paul says, 'put on the mind of Christ' (Phil 2:5). The act of putting on the sender's mind is participating in his will and keeping one's own will intact. It is similar to understanding the incarnation and the dual personalities of Christ being divine and human. He is fully divine and fully human. This understanding can be applied to the missionary as well. The missionary out to fully represent the sender as well as fully be present in his full capacity as he delivers the message. This is not merely an individual's activity but the whole community's activity. The whole community is on a Mission, i.e. the individual within the community who forms an integral part of the community focuses on the other, making the community a unique one with a total focus on the neighbour. In doing so, a new community is formed wherein an individual loses his individualness while maintaining his individualness in being a true missionary for Christ.

Church's Role in Mission

The Catholic Church has long been known for its mission to proclaim the Gospel to the world. This mission is not only for the clergy, but also for the laity, who play an important role in the life and work of the Church. The Second Vatican Council recognised this and underlined the necessity of laity participation in the mission of the Church. In carrying out the Church's mission, the Council also acknowledged the significance of collaboration among all members of the Church, including clergy, religious, and laity. This cooperative endeavour is referred to as "community in mission with synodality."

Pope Francis has called for a 'synodal Church' that listens to the voices of all its members, claiming that "the entire Church is required to evangelise the entire Church" (Evangelii Gaudium 33). This perspective views the Church as a community of believers rather than a hierarchical entity. Every member of this community is important and has a role to play in the Church's mission. Pope Francis has been a strong advocate for synodality in the Church. In his apostolic exhortation, *Evangelii Gaudium* wrote that "all the baptized, whatever their position in the Church or their level of instruction in the faith, are agents of evangelization" (EG 120). He also emphasized the importance of collaboration among all members of the Church in carrying out the Church's mission, stating that "the whole Church is needed to evangelize the whole Church" (EG 33).

Christ in Mission

Christ's mission on earth was to spread the Good News of the Gospel and save all humanity. Jesus accomplished this by establishing a community of disciples who shared his mission and continued his work after his death and resurrection. The Church is the community of believers carrying Christ's mission on earth through synodality. The Church's dedication to synodality reflects its commitment to Christ's mission. In a synodal Church, all members are called to actively engage in the life and work of the Church, and decisions are made through a collaborative effort involving all members of the Church. This method represents the Church's community, collegial, and dialogical nature, which is founded on Christ's own mission. We can see in the Bible the necessity of community in carrying out Christ's mission. "For where two or three are gathered in my name, there am I among them," Jesus declares in Matthew 18:20. This phrase underlines the value of community and the presence of Christ within it. We are not alone when we work together in the Church; Christ is with us, leading and empowering us to carry out his mission.

Poor in Mission

There are numerous missions within the Church's mission that are interconnected and attempt to achieve the same goal. One of these missions within a mission is the call to serve the poor and the marginalized. The Church's responsibility to serve the poor and marginalised includes meeting their physical needs and tackling the underlying causes of poverty and marginalisation. Working for social justice, supporting human rights, and advocating for the dignity of all people are all part of this. "Love of God and love of neighbour have become one: in the least of the brethren we find Jesus himself, and in Jesus we find God," Pope Benedict XVI wrote in *Deus Caritas Est* (DCE 15). This love for the impoverished is central to the Church's mission and reflects God's love and compassion for all people. The mission within the Church is the mission to poor. Keeping in mind the mission of Christ himself, this mission is essential for the future of the Church, as the poor who are marginalized need to be got into the mainstream so as their views too are included in the decision making since they too are members of the Church. Synodality is a crucial strategy for ensuring that the mission to the poor and oppressed is inclusive and collaborative. This entails hearing the voices of those most affected by poverty and marginalisation and including them in decision-making. It also entails collaborating as a community to address the underlying causes of poverty and marginalisation, rather than simply offering temporary assistance.

Conclusion

In identifying the true purpose of one's life, one can understand that participating in the mission of Christ along with the community is the basis of Christian living. To understand Christ in others and be another Christ is the mission. Being a part of a community and yet sent to the community of the world at large is the focus of the mission. The Father, Son and Holy Spirit being a perfect community are a model for us to emulate. The trinity participates in communion with its members but also maintains their individualness and participates with the human community with love and mercy. So are we members of a community called to participate and be the mission of Christ to the other through communion with Christ and with the neighbour. The mission is to be Christ, for Christ is the mission of the community, which is on the move towards being another Christ. Thus the Church's mission, though being multifaceted in action is ideologically one, i.e. to be another Christ in the world and Synodality is a process wherein we attempt to develop a vision wherein we see Christ in one another.

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